

Measuring the Flow Properties of Secondary Plastics

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ABSTRACT: Recycling of plastics, particularly in high-value applications, is essential for sustainable resource management and achieving climate targets. A critical challenge lies in developing robust processing methods that ensure consistent feeding of secondary raw materials into recycling machinery. After separation, sorting and cleaning, secondary plastics exist as irregularly shaped particles such as ground material, flakes or fibre agglomerates. Their complex flow characteristics defy conventional theoretical assessments and design calculations, necessitating reliance on empirical trial-and-error approaches. This often leads to inefficient equipment design or configuration, frequent operational interruptions and protracted development times. This study builds on practical insights gained through expert knowledge based on previous project applications to systematically investigate the flow and conveying behaviour of ground secondary plastics material.

1 INTRODUCTION

To improve the quality and uptake-rate of secondary plastics in the market, some technological challenges along the value chain must first be addressed. Similar to the processing of virgin plastic materials, the co-rotating twin-screw extruder is the standard compounding equipment for secondary plastics as well. However, the plastics recycling process also involves additional prior operations such as, separation, sorting, cleaning and comminution (grinding, shredding etc.) However, during comminution, secondary plastics acquire a heterogenous particle shape- and size distribution as is the case with regrinds, flakes and fibre agglomerates. This makes secondary plastics very difficult to convey because they defy conventional theoretical considerations of bulk plastic materials flow behaviour and associated design calculations. Apart from the well documented challenge of impurities arising from inaccurate separation, the “unpredictable” flow behaviour of secondary plastics also affects the process efficiency and product quality negatively (Kohlgrüber et al. 2021, Niessner 2022, Carson & Petro 2005; Markarian 2004).

2 STATUS QUO

While there are a few characterisation methods available for secondary plastics, most are focussed on quantifying the amount of impurities within a recycled material. In designing process equipment such as hoppers and silos conventional methods such as the measurement of: bulk density, tapped density, angle of repose, critical orifice diameter, particle size distribution and various characteristic values from shear cell tests are used (Aulton & Taylor 2013, Schulze 2021). All design considerations are based on free-flowing quasi-spherical particles which is far from the reality of secondary plastic particle size- and shape distributions. It is common for comminuted secondary plastic materials to be subjected to an extra processing step, where they are melted and regrinded into pellets of a narrow shape- and size distribution. To avoid the extra processing step, trial -and -error methods have to be relied upon, due to a lack of theoretical physical-mathematical models that accurately describe the flow behaviour of such materials. While trial-and-error methods have worked out well in the past, the demand for higher recycling efficiency is rising. Furthermore, this leads to an unsustainable over-reliance on already scarce highly experienced personnel.

Fig. 1: Status quo process steps of secondary plastics

3 MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Materials

Four different materials samples have been investigated in this study, including a Poly(lactic acid) (PLA) virgin material, a Polyoxymethylene (POM) virgin material as well as their respective regrind materials. Their particle morphologies and size distribution have been characterised as summarized in table 1.

Tab. 1: Particle morphologies and size distributions

Property	POM sec	POM virgin	PLA sec	PLA virgin
D50 Particle Size (µm)	5980	3975	7530	4009
Particle shape	irregular	lenticular	irregular	lenticular

3.2 Experiments

Dynamic flow characteristics of the materials were measured using an FT4 universal powder tester from Freeman Technology. The FT4 measures the flow resistance of a bulk material while it is in motion. A precision blade rotates and moves downwards through the bulk material to create an accurate flow pattern. This causes thousands of particles to interact or flow relative to each other. In addition to the dynamic methods, it offers additional measurement options. These include a shear cell to measure the shear strength of powders and a wall friction kit to quantify the behaviour of the powder on the wall of the process material. Further accessories are available to measure bulk material properties such as density, compressibility and air permeability. Further details of the FT4 methodologies can be found in other literatures (Freeman & Fu 2008).

All samples were preconditioned before each measurement. However, due to a recurring torque and force overload issue, the standard test was modified to cater for the larger particles of the materials investigated. The lower height was increased to 6mm. Furthermore, the 48mm blade was used in combination with the 62mm split vessel.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The basic flowability energy for the POM secondary material is with $1640,3 \pm 4,36$ mJ higher than the POM virgin material at $412,7 \pm 4,80$ mJ. This is largely due to mechanical interlocking arising from the irregular shape of the constitutive bulk solid particles. The same phenomenon is observed with the PLA material whereby the secondary material has a higher Basic Flowability Energy (BFE) value with a similar difference to the virgin material of 1296.7 mJ. A similar trend is observed with the specific energy values. Higher values are observed for the secondary materials

indicating that more energy is required to set the materials into motion. Data on the flow rate index indicates that all (virgin and secondary) materials exhibited a pseudoplastic flow behaviour (<1). The same observation applies to the stability index values.

Fig. 2: Basic flowability energy in mJ

Fig. 3: Specific energy in mJ/g

Fig. 4: Stability Index, Flow Rate Index and Conditioned Bulk Density

5 OUTLOOK

With the feasibility of measuring the flow properties of secondary plastics confirmed, the next step of correlating the data collected to process conditions will follow. As a next step, the same materials will be subjected to dosing experiments to assess the achievable accuracies and constancies based on the NAMUR NA 40 Worksheet of 2006 on the dosing accuracy of continuous scales.

REFERENCES

- Aulton, Michael E.; Taylor, Kevin (2013): Aulton's pharmaceuticals. The design and manufacture of medicines. 4th edition / edited by Michael E. Aulton and Kevin M.G. Taylor. Edinburgh: Churchill Livingstone/Elsevier.
- Carson, John. W.; Petro, Greg (2005): How to design efficient and reliable feeders for bulk solids. Jenike & Johanson Inc., Flow of Solids Newsletters. Online verfügbar unter <https://www.web-tech.com.au/wp-content/uploads/Design-efficient-feeders.pdf>, zuletzt geprüft am 01.12.2022.
- Freeman, R.; Fu, Xiaowei (2008): Characterisation of powder bulk, dynamic flow and shear properties in relation to die filling. In: *Powder Metallurgy* 51 (3), S. 196–201. DOI: 10.1179/174329008X324115
- Kohlgrüber, Klemens; Bierdel, Michael; Rust, Harald (2021): *Plastics Compounding and Polymer Processing. Fundamentals, Machines, Equipment, Application Technology*. Cincinnati, Ohio: Hanser Publications (Hanser eLibrary). Online verfügbar unter <https://www.hanser-elibrary.com/doi/book/10.3139/9781569908389>.
- Markarian, Jennifer (2004): Dosing and blending - getting the right mix. In: *Plastics, Additives and Compounding* 6 (6), S. 26–31. DOI: 10.1016/S1464-391X(04)00302-2.
- Niessner, Norbert (Hg.) (2022): *Recycling of plastics*. Hanser Publications. Munich: Hanser Publishers.
- Schulze, Dietmar (2021): *Powders and Bulk Solids*. Cham: Springer International Publishing.

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